

Green Human Resource Management:

A Bibliometric Analysis Based on Dimensions Platform

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the publication trends, citations, top journals, top authors and top areas of study in context of Green Human Resource Management (HRM) through bibliometric analysis. This study has used bibliometric review method by analysing the data of 413 researches from 2010 to 2020. The data was collected from Dimensions database and was analyzed on VOSviewer software. The study has found an increase in number of publications from just five articles published in 2010 to 118 articles in 2020. Also, publications on Green HRM have witnessed enormous growth from 2016 to 2020. The study has identified the following information: most influential researches on Green HRM on the basis of citation count through citation analysis, most prominent journals publishing Green HRM articles, prominent authors publishing Green HRM articles and top subject areas publishing Green HRM related researches. The study found that Green HRM is connected not only to management and commerce but also to areas like biological sciences, engineering and psychology and cognitive sciences which signifies that Green HRM topic is multidisciplinary in nature. The review is an attempt to give an overview of Green HRM to researchers and identify relevant areas for further researches.

Keywords: *Bibliometric, Citation analysis, Green HRM, Leading journals, Prominent authors, Publication trends*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has created a challenging environment for organizations. Organizations are finding it difficult to keep their businesses running and are continuously trying to find new best practices to do so. There is a need of coordinated efforts from all the departments of an organization in tackling the challenges caused by COVID-19 pandemic.

Organizations are now focusing on efficient use of resources. Interventions from human resource management perspective can play an important role in mitigating the impact of COVID-19. One of the interventions is Green Human Resource Management (HRM), whose need was felt more during the current pandemic. Wehrmeyer in 1996 introduced the concept of Green Human Resource Management (HRM). A systemic and planned alignment of human resource management practices with organizational environmental goals is known as Green HRM (Jabbour, 2013). Green HRM in business consists of such HRM activities which boost the sustainable use of available resources and avoid any environmental harm from any business operation (Zoogah, 2011). Emphasizing on Green HRM can help organizations in mitigating the impact of COVID-19.

This study is an attempt to provide an overview of Green HRM through bibliometric analysis of studies on Green HRM. Bibliometric analysis is a process which involves application of various statistical methods to explain a research topic (De Bakker et al., 2005; Bouyssou & Marchant, 2011). Bibliometric analysis is defined as the process of analysing a body of literature through quantitative and statistical methods (Bates and Maack, 2009). Dimensions database is used in this study. For citation analysis, VOSviewer software is used. VOSviewer software examines the relationship between most cited authors and collaboration among them, between authors and coordination among countries and institutions (Hoppen & De Souza Vanz, 2016). The rest of the paper is designed as follows: section 2 and 3 deal with literature review and the objectives of the study respectively. Sections 4 deals with research methodology used for the study and section 5 presents the findings. Section 6 includes the conclusion, limitation and future scope.

Literature Review

Green human resource management (Green HRM) focusses on protecting environment through human resource management (HRM) i.e. how HRM can contribute to green outcomes (Khan and Muktar, 2020). Green HRM emphasizes on how the organizations can create competitive advantage by preserving the environment (Elkington, 1998). Green HRM emphasizes that the human resource department of any organization can play an important role in formulating such policies which are environment friendly (Renwick, D. et al., 2008). Green HRM involves adoption of a green perspective and making use of green

communication channels in an organization (Tang et al., 2018). Green HRM practices affect lives and performances of employees in a positive way (Latan et al., 2018). Organizations prefer to link HRM with the environment because through Green HRM activities, organizations start focussing on the environmental damage caused by their activities and become more responsible for sustainable outcomes (Koberg & Longoni, 2019). Green HRM encourages employees in involving themselves in the environmental management activities (Renwick, D. et al., 2008; Renwick D.W. et al., 2013). Green HRM practices make the employees happy and workplace environment friendly (Shrivastava, 1994).

Bibliometric analysis provides complete information about a particular topic (Van Eck & Waltman, 2017; White & McCain, 1998). Bibliometric analysis involves use of various mathematical and statistical techniques for examining and scanning documents on any particular topic (Garfield, 1955). Identifying the database is the initial step in bibliometric analysis. There are various databases which can be used like ISI, Google Scholar, Dimensions, Web of Science (WOS) and Scopus databases. Bibliometric analysis can be defined as the study of research outputs and their patterns by applying various quantitative and statistical methods (Bates and Maack, 2009). One of the assumptions of bibliometric analysis is that all researches are published in reputable journals or databases from where they can be cited by other researchers and subsequently accessed (Kokol et al., 2015). The main purpose of bibliometric analysis is to highlight all the research work in a particular discipline by analysing the patterns in the research publications (Hazarika et al., 2003). Bibliometric analysis involves use of quantitative methods in describing, monitoring, evaluating, and analysing research publications and thus improving the quality of reviews (Zupic & Cater, 2015). Bibliometric method has gained more importance due to the availability and presence of online databases such as Scopus, Web of Science and Dimensions (Zupic & Cater, 2015).

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to present a comprehensive bibliometric review of Green HRM. The broad objective is achieved through the following specific research objectives-

- Research objective 1: To identify the publication trends with respect to time in the field of Green HRM

- Research objective 2: To identify the most influential research papers in the field of Green HRM through citation analysis
- Research objective 3: To identify the top journals with respect to publications in the field of Green HRM
- Research objective 4: To identify the prominent authors in the field of Green HRM with respect to publications
- Research objective 5: To identify the top areas of Green HRM research with respect to publications

Research Methodology

For achieving the objectives, the study has used quantitative research and bibliometric review method. The study has analyzed the data of 413 researches published from 2010 to 2020. The data was collected from Dimensions database. Bibliometric analysis is an extensively practiced approach to study about the origin of any research topic (Li, Wu, and Wu, 2017). This study makes use of tools like publication trends and citation network analysis. VOSviewer software is used for data analysis. VOSviewer software provides a map in which the relatedness of items can be examined by the distance between them.

Findings

The findings of the study, with respect to the five research objectives discussed above, are presented below.

Trend of Publication from 2010 to 2020

Illustration 1 shows Dimensions data on Green HRM publications from the period 2010 to 2020. There has been an increase in publications i.e. from just five articles published in 2010 to 118 articles in 2020. Publications on Green HRM have seen huge growth from 2016 to 2020. Out of total 430 publications, 259 papers-which is 60% of total publications- were published in the past three years. This increasing trend suggests that the term Green HRM has gained importance among the researchers.

Illustration 1: Annual publication trend of 430 papers, during the period 2010–2020, retrieved from Dimensions database

Most Influential Research Papers in Green HRM as per Citation Analysis

S. No.	Research Paper	Citations
1	Renwick (2012)	446
2	Jackson (2011)	244
3	Jabbour (2016)	206
4	Bohdanowicz (2011)	179
5	Dumont (2016)	159
6	Singh (2020)	114
7	Antonioli (2013)	114
8	Renwick (2015)	110
9	Masri (2017)	104
10	Guerci (2015a)	97
11	Pinzone (2016)	93
12	Jabbour (2019)	90
13	Roscoe (2019)	84
14	Ren (2017)	83
15	Nejati (2017)	83

Illustration 2: Top 15 research papers on Green HRM on the basis of citation count, during period 2010–2020, retrieved from Dimensions database

Leading Journals Publishing on Green HRM

The third objective of this study was to identify the most influential journals publishing papers on Green HRM. From 2010 to 2020, total of 430 publications were dispersed across many journals. Illustration 4 shows the list of most prominent journals publishing on Green HRM. Top 15 journals have published 30% of the total publications. The Journal of Cleaner Production has published highest number of research articles, followed by Dyes and Pigments and RSC Advances.

Illustration 4: Most prominent journals publishing Green HRM articles, during the period 2010–2020, retrieved from Dimensions database

Prominent Authors in Green HRM

Bibliometric analysis helps in finding out the prominent authors in a particular field (McCain, 1990; Nerur et al., 2008; White & McCain, 1998). Illustration 5 shows the list of top contributors based on their number of publications. Sreekantha Babu Jonnalagadda and Suresh Maddila lead the list with 15 publications each, followed by Charbel José Chiappetta Jabbour with 11 publications and Mohd Yusoff Yusliza with 8 publications.

S. No	Researchers	Publications
1	Sreekantha Babu Jonnalagadda	15
2	Suresh Maddila	15
3	Charbel José Chiappetta Jabbour	11
4	Mohd Yusoff Yusliza	8
5	Surya Narayana Maddila	6
6	Maria Halabalaki	6
7	Michael Müller-Camen	5
8	Giulia Graziani	5
9	Nagaraju Kerru	5
10	Xu Xu	5

Illustration 5: Top authors & their Green HRM publications during 2010–2020, retrieved from Dimensions database.

Top Areas of Green HRM Research

Illustration 6 suggests that the top area of Green HRM research is Chemical Science followed by Management, Commerce and Tourism. Illustration 6 shows that the subject of Green HRM is connected not only to Management and Commerce but also to areas like Biological Science, Engineering and Psychology and Cognitive Sciences. This signifies that Green HRM topic is multidisciplinary in nature. Illustration 6 shows an interesting fact that there is lack of literature in other fields like Economics and Physical Sciences.

Illustration 6: Number of Green HRM publications in top subject areas during period 2010–2020, retrieved from Dimensions database.

Conclusion, Limitation and Future Scope

The field of Green HRM holds great importance for industry and academia. This study has tried to cast some light on bibliometric analysis of Green HRM between 2010 and 2020 by using data from Dimensions database. This study provides a comprehensive overview about Green HRM by determining the publication trends, top research articles, top journals, top authors and top areas of study. The study has used Dimensions database which is a limitation of this study. For further studies, researchers can consider other databases like Scopus and Web of Science for bibliometric analysis.

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